

Crystallographic characterization and microstructure study of perovskite phase : $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1-1.0$)

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Abstract : Perovskite phases of iron and niobium substituted calcium titanate (hereafter CTFN) have been synthesized by a combination of precursor and ceramic method. The crystal structure of $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1-1.0$) phases has been investigated using General Structure Analysis System (GSAS) programming. These phases crystallize in the orthorhombic system with space group Pbnm and $Z = 4$. Approximately 12 mole% of cations could be loaded into the matrix without significant changes of the three-dimensional framework structure. Powder diffraction data have been subjected to Rietveld refinement to arrive at a satisfactory convergence of R-factors. The unit cell parameters and cell volume increase regularly with increasing level of substitution on titanium site. The polyhedral distortions and bond valence calculation based on bond strength analysis have been reported. Morphology of the samples has been investigated by SEM and TEM analysis. Frequency dependent dielectric behavior of the material has been observed.

Keywords : X-Ray diffraction, crystal structure, impedance spectroscopy, microstructure.

Introduction

Perovskite structured calcium titanates are well known for their property of cationic substitution on A and B sites¹⁻⁴. Their properties can be modified by controlled defect chemistry to suit specific applications. This is achieved either by doping with aliovalent ions or by a change in the oxygen non-stoichiometry. Such materials have received attention due to their variety of applications such as component of dielectric resonator in wireless communication systems⁵, capacitors⁶, microwave material, varistors⁷⁻⁹, electrochemical oxygen separator¹⁰ and electrode material¹¹. They dominate low to high permittivity range of microwave dielectrics and temperature stable ceramics providing high quality factor¹²⁻¹⁴. Moreover, the versatility of perovskite structure opens up possibility of making solid solutions designed to achieve specific requirements. CaTiO_3 has been also identified as a major constituent of precursor materials for immobilization of nuclear wastes in synroc (synthetic rock) technology¹⁵⁻¹⁷. On account of wide ranging potential applications of modified perovskite phase of CaTiO_3 it was thought worthwhile to study its solid state reaction with Fe^{3+} and Nb^{5+} . To study the structure property relationship, this communication focuses on the crystallographic data and

microstructure of iron and niobium substituted calcium titanates having different levels of substitutions on B site. Frequency and temperature dependence of dielectric constant and tangent loss of $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1$) has been investigated for possible application as dielectric material.

Experimental

Ceramic route synthesis of $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ phases :

Calculated quantities of AR grade CaCO_3 , TiO_2 , Nb_2O_5 and Fe_2O_3 for the stoichiometry $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1) were thoroughly mixed with about 10 ml of 1,2,3-propane triol to form a semisolid paste. On repeated grinding and sintering the semisolid paste at 1250 °C in a muffle furnace for 12 h, densification of material takes place to form phase pure polycrystalline solid solution.

Characterization :

The materials have been characterized by powder X-ray diffraction method recorded between $2\theta = 10^\circ-90^\circ$ on a Pan Analytical diffractometer (XPRT-PRO) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at step size of $2\theta = 0.017^\circ$ and a fixed

counting time of 5 s/step. Morphology of the specimens has been investigated using scanning and transmission electron microscopy. SEM has been carried out on an electron microscope system (HITACHI S-3400) equipped with ThermoNoran ultra dry detector facility for energy dispersive X-ray (EDAX) analysis. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) was carried out with a PHILIPS CM200 analytical instrument operated between 20–200 kV.

Electrical properties of $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1$) have been investigated by a.c. impedance method carried out on computer controlled impedance analyzer HIOKI LCR HITESTER 3532-50 between the frequency range from 42 Hz to 5 MHz. Impedance, capacitance and dissipation factor were collected as a function of frequency in the range of ambient temperature to 300 °C over heating and cooling cycles. The sintered pellet's flat surfaces were painted with high purity conducting silver paste followed by drying at 300 °C. After electroding, the sample in the form of circular disc (1.29 cm diameter and 0.30 cm thickness) was placed along with the sample holder in the computer interfaced dry well type furnace for electrical measurements.

Results and discussion

Crystallographic data :

The powder XRD data shows that solid solution of

compositions $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6$ and 0.8) are isostructural to CaTiO_3 ¹⁸ but beyond $x = 0.6$, minor secondary phase of calcium iron niobium oxide (*marked) begins to appear along with calcium titanate (Fig. 1). The unit cell parameters of $\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$, which crystallize in orthorhombic symmetry (space group Pbnm, $a \approx b \approx \sqrt{2}a_p$, $c \approx 2a_p$, $Z = 4$) were refined using GSAS software¹⁹. The reflection conditions for this space group were verified from the International Table for X-Ray Crystallography¹⁸ and further checked for presence of 021 and absence of 201 reflections, which is not allowed²⁰. In addition to this, both odd-odd-odd and odd-odd-even reflections are present in the title phase indicating that the oxygen octahedra are tilted both in phase as well as anti phase²¹. Increase in iron and niobium content results in increase of the cell dimension of the crystal. The lattice expansion is expected from substitution of Ti^{4+} by $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Nb}^{5+}$ on B site because in the octahedral coordination the ionic radii of Fe^{3+} and Nb^{5+} are 0.064 and 0.069 nm respectively against 0.0605 nm for Ti^{4+} . A satisfactory structure convergence has been obtained after refining the data by Rietveld method²² (Fig. 2 and Table 1). The normal probability plot for the histogram gives nearly a straight line indicating that the I_0 and I_c values are for the most part normally distributed.

In this structure model of CTFN, Ca cations occupy

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of CTFN samples sintered at 1250 °C for 12 h. *marked secondary phase is due to calcium iron niobium oxide.

Fig. 2. Rietveld refinement plot of CTFN, observed (plus) and calculated (continuous line), differences (bottom) between the observed and calculated intensities, vertical bars represent the Bragg's positions.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for CTFN calcined phases at room temperature

Parameters	x						
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
Lattice constants :							
<i>a</i>	5.37754(21)	5.3953(4)	5.3978(5)	5.4025(5)	5.4163(8)	5.5267(6)	5.62304(32)
<i>b</i>	5.43654(23)	5.4468(4)	5.4491(6)	5.4607(6)	5.4703(7)	5.3494(5)	5.51590(26)
<i>c</i>	7.6381(4)	7.6491(8)	7.6516(13)	7.6660(14)	7.6515(20)	7.5923(7)	7.8563(4)
<i>R_p</i>	0.1297	0.1018	0.0946	0.0825	0.0750	0.0834	0.0787
<i>R_{wp}</i>	0.1683	0.1332	0.1239	0.1120	0.0957	0.1110	0.1066
<i>R_{expected}</i>	0.1133	0.0945	0.0905	0.0822	0.0742	0.0701	0.0679
<i>RF²</i>	0.13076	0.15927	0.15339	0.12103	0.12739	0.13361	0.23861
Volume of unit cell	223.303(11)	224.788(18)	225.057(26)	226.161(28)	226.71(4)	224.466(35)	243.673(14)
<i>S</i> (GoF)	1.490	1.41	1.37	1.37	1.29	1.59	1.58
DWd	1.032	1.145	1.165	1.171	1.288	0.841	-
Unit cell	554.499	567.149	580.627	587.612	608.842	628.633	649.8
formula weight							
Density _{X-ray}	4.123	4.190	4.284	4.314	4.460	4.65	-
Slope	1.345	1.3106	1.2771	1.2086	1.2053	1.3858	1.3076
Structure	Orthorhombic						
Space group	Pbnm						
Z	4						
$\alpha = \beta = \gamma$	90°						

$$R_p = \frac{\sum y_i(\text{obs}) - y_i(\text{cal})}{\sum y_i(\text{obs})}, R_{wp} = \left\{ \frac{\sum w_i (y_i(\text{obs}) - y_i(\text{cal}))^2}{\sum w_i (y_i(\text{obs}))^2} \right\}^{1/2}, R_{\text{expected}} = \left[(N - P) / \sum w_i y_i^2 \right]^{1/2}, S = R_{wp} / R_{\text{expected}}$$

$y_{i(o)}$ and $y_{i(c)}$ are observed and calculated intensities at profile point i , respectively. w_i is a weight for each step i . N is the no. of parameters refined.

the distorted cuboctahedron generated by the eight corner sharing oxygen octahedra which results in eight coordinate environment while the Ti/Fe, Nb cations are inside the oxygen octahedra in a six coordinate environment (Fig. 3a). The inter-atomic distances between Ti(1) and the apex oxygen atoms of the octahedron have been found to be between 2.05246 to 2.11964 Å while the two sets of planar oxygen bond distances Ti(1)–O(5) vary from 1.9064 to 2.06447 Å respectively (Fig. 3b and Appendix-1). For the given coordination number the calculated M–O distances are close to their standard values of metal

oxygen distances in the corresponding metal oxides. Inter atomic distances data indicate slight distortion of the TiO_6 framework from the ideal cubic symmetry of perovskites due to tilting of the oxygen octahedra surrounding the Ti atoms. Effect of this distortion is reflected in lowering of coordination number of Ca to eight against the ideal value of 12.

The bond valences²³ (V_i) vary between 2.47 to 2.75 for Ca and 4.45–5.07 for Ti respectively. The calculated valences V_i based on bond strength analysis²⁴ suggest residual compression of Ca–O and Ti–O bonds. The compression is primarily attributed to the partial occupancy by the marginally smaller cations (Fe^{3+} , Nb^{5+}) in the perovskite framework. In addition, the displacement of the Ca cation due to octahedral tilting also contributes to the compression of the A-site species²⁵. The average crystallite size was determined using Scherrer's method. For compositions $x = 0.1$ –1.0 it varied from 15–200 nm along major reflecting planes.

Positional coordinates, isotropic parameters, bonds angles (Appendix-2) and inter planar spacing along with their observed and calculated structure factors have been extracted from crystal information file after final cycle of Reitveld refinement.

SEM and TEM analysis :

The surface morphology of selected specimens investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) shows the grain size of 2–6 μm on the entire surface. The elemental distributions in the grains and grain boundaries have been measured by energy dispersive X-ray (EDAX) analysis (Fig. 4a). In TEM analysis the powder was observed in the form of non uniform shaped agglomerates. The particle diameter was found to be in the nano range (Fig. 5a). The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the specimen shows concentric rings in the diffraction pattern, which confirms the polycrystalline nature of the material (Fig. 5b).

Impedance analysis :

Dielectric properties of $\text{CaTi}_{0.9}(\text{Fe}_{0.05}\text{Nb}_{0.05})\text{O}_3$ have been studied as a function of frequency and temperature. The material exhibits almost temperature independent dielectric constant after 50 °C. The frequency dependence of impedance, dielectric constant (ϵ') and tangent loss (δ) at different temperature is shown in Figs. 6, 7a and 7b

Fig. 3. (a) CTFN structure viewed along 'a' direction. The spheres represent Ca cations, Ti/(Fe, Nb) cations are enclosed by the octahedra. Oxygen ions are situated at the corners of the octahedra. (b) ORTEP view of CTFN showing six coordination of Ti atom along with their bond lengths.

Appendix-1. Selected inter-atomic distances (Å) for CTFN phase

Bond distance	x						
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Ca-O1	2.34(9)	2.33(17)	2.34(24)	2.35(24)	2.35(26)	2.31(18)	2.33(10)
Ca-O1	2.22(8)	2.20(16)	2.22(21)	2.23(21)	2.23(32)	2.27(23)	2.21(12)
Ca-O2	2.65(7)*2	2.67(15)*2	2.66(21)*2	2.66(23)*2	2.66(31)*2	2.65(15)*2	2.78(9)*2
Ca-O2	2.28(7)*2	2.30(15)*2	2.29(22)*2	2.29(24)*2	2.29(33)*2	2.28(13)*2	2.40(8)*2
Ca-O2	2.67(10)*2	2.67(20)*2	2.67(30)*2	2.68(33)*2	2.68(5)*2	2.67(17)*2	2.70(10)*2
Ti/M-O1	2.06(10)*2	2.06(20)*2	2.06(29)*2	2.06(33)*2	2.06(5)*2	2.05(16)*2	2.12(10)*2
Ti/M-O2	1.91(6)*2	1.91(11)*2	1.91(15)*2	1.92(15)*2	1.92(21)*2	1.93(15)*2	1.97(8)*2
Ti/M-O2	2.01(6)*2	2.02(12)*2	2.02(17)*2	2.02(17)*2	2.02(19)*2	2.01(14)*2	2.06(7)*2
Ca-Ti/M	3.21(11)*2	3.45(23)*2	3.45(33)*2	3.45(34)*2	3.46(4)*2	3.39(23)*2	3.51(13)*2
Ca-Ti/M	3.20(10)*2	3.21(21)*2	3.21(30)*2	3.22(32)*2	3.22(4)*2	3.17(21)*2	3.26(12)*2
Ca-Ti/M	3.41(11)*2	3.22(20)*2	3.21(28)*2	3.20(30)*2	3.21(4)*2	3.24(25)*2	3.41(14)*2
Ca-Ti/M	3.44(12)*2	3.40(21)*2	3.41(29)*2	3.42(31)*2	3.42(5)*2	3.47(27)*2	3.46(15)*2
Ca-Ca	3.64(11)*2	3.68(21)*2	3.66(29)*2	3.66(29)*2	3.66(35)*2	3.66(25)*2	3.89(14)*2
Ca-Ca	4.01(12)*2	3.99(22)*2	4.01(31)*2	4.03(31)*2	4.04(4)*2	4.046(29)*2	3.98(15)*2
Ca-Ca	3.84(21)*2	3.84(4)*2	3.84(6)*2	3.85(7)*2	3.66(35)*2	4.046(29)*2	3.94(21)*2
Polyhedral distortion							
CaO ₈	61.84	62.16	9.93	10.08	9.31	6.22	6.22
TiO ₆	10.23	11.17	61.17	61.66	60.80	59.19	61.42
M = Fe and Nb; $\Delta = 1/n \sum \{(R_i - R_m)/(R_m)\}^2$							

Appendix-2. O-M-O bond angles (deg.) in CTFN polycrystalline powder

O-M-O angle	x						
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
O1-Ca-O1	83.59(18)	84.27(35)	83.86(5)	83.59(5)	83.56(6)	82.22(4)	85.98(23)
O1-Ca-O2	69.49(21)*2	69.52(4)*2	69.59(6)*2	69.49(6)*2	69.48(7)*2	70.95(5)*2	70.22(25)*2
O1-Ca-O2	130.92(13)*2	130.44(32)*2	130.52(5)*2	130.46(5)*2	130.56(7)*2	130.51(29)*2	129.86(16)*2
O1-Ca-O2	60.71(13)*2	61.01(26)*2	60.85(4)*2	60.69(4)*2	60.60(6)*2	60.46(24)*2	62.08(13)*2
O1-Ca-O2	130.92(13)*2	131.50(26)*2	131.20(4)*2	130.94(4)*2	131.02(6)*2	130.51(26)*2	133.58(15)*2
O1-Ca-O2	107.54(16)*2	107.86(31)*2	107.61(4)*2	107.55(4)*2	107.61(6)*2	108.77(4)*2	109.81(22)*2
O1-Ca-O2	67.78(16)*2	68.23(30)*2	67.92(4)*2	67.77(4)*2	67.69(6)*2	131.52(26)*2	92.52(4)*2
O2-Ca-O2	67.27(30)*2	66.94(6)*2	67.16(8)*2	67.29(9)*2	67.40(11)*2	66.65(4)*2	64.69(31)*2
O2-Ca-O2	124.12(26)*2	124.24(5)*2	124.27(7)*2	124.09(8)*2	124.00(10)*2	125.09(5)*2	125.04(27)*2
O2-Ca-O2	168.31(4)*2	168.27(8)*2	168.18(12)*2	168.31(13)*2	168.29(16)*2	168.45(8)*2	167.99(4)*2
O2-Ca-O2	63.32(28)*2	63.44(5)*2	63.46(8)*2	63.36(8)*2	63.52(10)*2	65.05(6)*2	64.28(33)*2
O2-Ca-O2	121.27(26)*2	91.0(6)*2	91.0(8)*2	121.24(7)*2	121.09(8)*2	119.44(6)*2	116.09(35)*2
O2-Ca-O2	77.22(35)*2	120.30(5)*2	77.09(10)*2	77.17(11)*2	76.94(12)*2	76.61(6)*2	75.45(4)*2
O2-Ca-O2	78.77(35)*2	78.89(7)*2	78.86(10)*2	90.94(8)*2	79.04(12)*2	79.50(6)*2	79.07(4)*2
O2-Ca-O2	93.01(4)*2	92.31(7)*2	92.63(10)*2	92.96(11)*2	92.73(13)*2	92.56(6)*2	90.26(4)*2
O2-Ca-O2	108.02(35)	108.67(7)*2	108.26(10)*2	107.97(11)*2	107.74(12)*2	107.02(7)*2	110.93(4)*2
O1-Ti-O1	180.0	180.0	180.0	179.98	180.0	180.0	180.0
O1-Ti-O2	92.12(15)*2	92.16(30)*2	92.17(4)*2	92.13(4)*2	92.22(6)*2	93.21(4)*2	102.64(17)*2
O1-Ti-O2	102.49(16)*2	102.52(31)*2	102.53(4)*2	102.51(5)*2	102.62(7)*2	102.95(30)*2	92.76(20)*2
O1-Ti-O2	87.88(15)*2	87.83(30)*2	87.83(4)*2	87.87(4)*2	87.78(6)*2	93.20(7)*2	87.23(20)*2
O2-Ti-O2	77.51(16)*2	77.47(31)*2	77.47(4)*2	77.48(5)*2	77.38(7)*2	77.046(30)*2	77.36(17)*2
O2-Ti-O2	89.07(30)*2	88.99(6)*2	88.99(8)*2	89.07(8)*2	90.98(10)*2	86.80(7)*2	87.49(4)*2
O2-Ti-O2	180.0, 179.97	180*2	180.0*2	179.97*2	180.0*2	180.0, 179.96	180.0*2
O1-Ti-O2	90.93(30)*2	76.84(7)*2	120.87(7)*2	78.82(11)*2	89.02(10)*2	86.79(4)*2	69.40(19)*2

The * denotes multiplicity of bonds and angles. The values in parentheses denote estimated values.

Fig. 4. EDAX spectrum and SEM micrographs of CTFN ($x = 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1.0) samples.

Fig. 5. (a) TEM and (b) SAED image of CTFN ($x = 0.8$) sample.

Fig. 7. Frequency dependence of the dielectric constant and loss for CTFN ($x = 0.1$) sample.

Fig. 6. Impedance spectrum of CTFN ($x = 0.1$) powder.

respectively. The decreasing dielectric constant with increasing frequency can be attributed to the lagging of dipoles present in the material which is a typical Debye type behavior exhibited by most of the dielectric materials²⁶. The dielectric constant of CTFN is higher than the corresponding ϵ' value for CaTiO_3 ²⁷. At lower frequencies there is substantial dielectric loss but the loss decreases sharply with increase in frequency and reduces to 0.005 after 1×10^5 Hz (Fig. 7b). The variation of ϵ' and $\tan \delta$ may be attributed to hopping of trapped charge carriers, which resulted in an extra dielectric response in addition to dipole response²⁸.

Conclusions :

$\text{CaTi}_{1-x}(\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0.1-1.0$) samples were synthesized by standard ceramic technique. The phases crystallize in orthorhombic symmetry with local distortion and slight tilting of TiO_6 octahedron. The Rietveld plots represent a good structure fit between observed and calculated intensity with satisfactory R-factors. The lattice parameters and cell volume increase with increase in iron and niobium content. The substitution limit of Fe and Nb on Ti site of calcium titanate matrix was found to be ~ 12 mole%. The microstructure analysis and particle size calculation shows that the title compound crystallizes as a nano phase. The impedance study reveals that the material has frequency dependent dielectric constant. At lower frequencies both the dielectric constant and the loss factor is high but the trend is reversed at higher frequencies.

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